

Role of the active metal (Fe, Co and Ni) on the activity of Nd₂O₃-supported catalysts for ammonia synthesis

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ABSTRACT

Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni monometallic catalysts were synthesised and used in the ammonia synthesis reaction. The effect of active metal on the physicochemical and catalytic properties was investigated using, e.g., TPR, TPD, XRD, and STEM. The results showed that the kind of active metal used is the factor determining the catalytic activity in ammonia synthesis. The highest ammonia formation rate was exhibited by Co/Nd₂O₃, whereas the highest intrinsic reaction rate (reflected as the TOF value) was shown by Fe/Nd₂O₃. Ni/Nd₂O₃ showed almost no activity in ammonia synthesis. The high ammonia formation rate observed for Co/Nd₂O₃ was attributable to the well-distributed Co nanoparticles (NPs) on the Nd₂O₃ support. The Co NPs were less prone to sintering than Fe NPs under reaction conditions. Thus, although showing lower TOF than Fe NPs, the better distribution of Co NPs resulted in an improved ammonia formation rate. These findings highlight the importance of rational catalyst design for improving ammonia synthesis efficiency.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) is an essential chemical for the agricultural and industrial sectors. It is primarily used to produce fertilisers necessary to support the global food supply, as well as in the manufacturing of explosives, textiles, and pharmaceuticals. The Haber-Bosch (H-B) process, developed over a century ago, is the primary method for ammonia synthesis on a large scale, and iron-based catalysts are typically used in the process. However, the H-B process is highly energy-intensive, operating at high pressures (15–30 MPa) and temperatures (400–500 °C), contributing to significant greenhouse gas emissions. Such harsh conditions are required to overcome the energy barrier from the dissociation of a stable N≡N triple bond (bond energy of 941 kJ mol⁻¹). These account for around 2% of global energy consumption, highlighting the importance of developing more energy-efficient and sustainable methods for ammonia production [1–8].

Catalysts play a vital role in ammonia synthesis, reducing the energy required for the reaction to occur. Iron, ruthenium, and cobalt have been widely studied for ammonia synthesis. The activity of these metals can be illustrated through the volcano-shaped curve that represents the relationship between the metal-nitrogen binding energy and its activity

in ammonia synthesis [9–12]. The primary challenge for efficient NH₃ synthesis arises from the inverse relationship between the N₂ dissociation barrier and the desorption energy of NH_x intermediates on transition metals (TMs). Consequently, the NH₃ synthesis activity over TMs exhibits a volcano-shaped relationship with nitrogen adsorption energy. According to the volcano curve, Ru, with moderate nitrogen adsorption energy, is near the peak of this curve, demonstrating the highest catalytic activity. In contrast, other transition metals located on either side of this curve are less active, either because of the excessively strong or weak nitrogen adsorption, resulting in a higher NH_x desorption barrier or a higher N₂ dissociation barrier, respectively. Generally, an optimal catalyst for ammonia synthesis should activate N₂ easily and bind weakly with NH_x intermediates [9–12]. Ru and Os are the most active metals in ammonia synthesis, and the third is Fe. Co also catalyses ammonia synthesis but exhibits orders-of-magnitude lower activity than Ru, Os, and Fe. Mo and Ni show almost no activity in ammonia synthesis [9–12]. However, the activity of these metals can be improved by promotion. Metal promotion is the most effective strategy for enhancing the activity of ammonia synthesis catalysts [9–12].

Fe-based catalysts have traditionally been used in the industry due to their low cost, high mechanical strength, and relatively high activity

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[13–16]. Fe is the third most active metal after Ru and Os in ammonia synthesis [10], demonstrating moderate nitrogen binding energy, allowing for efficient nitrogen activation without significant inhibition of NH_x intermediates. Despite their robustness, the critical issue with iron catalysts is their requirement for high pressure and temperature, necessary to obtain high reaction rates.

Co and Ni, different from Fe, are located on the right-hand side of the volcano curve [10]. For elements at the right-hand of the volcano curve, a lower nitrogen binding energy is found, which facilitates the desorption of NH_x intermediates but, on the other hand, impedes N_2 dissociative activation [10]. As a result, catalysts require modifications, such as doping with electron-donating elements or combining with other metals (e.g., alloying with Fe since it is located on the other side of the volcano curve), to enhance activity [9]. Recent advances in cobalt-based systems have shown promise for further development [17–27]. The significant advances have been made both in the development of conventional supported Co catalysts, where the activities were much improved through support and promoter choice, as well as in the development of novel systems such as nitrides, carbides and intermetallics. Recently, ternary intermetallic compounds, especially LaCoSi, have drawn extensive attention for ammonia synthesis due to their specific structures and outstanding catalytic performance. Gong et al. [26] reported a stable ternary intermetallic compound, LaCoSi, that could shift the rate-determining step (RDS) of ammonia synthesis from the sluggish N_2 dissociation to the formation of NH_x under mild reaction conditions. LaCoSi was characterised by high catalytic activity, more than 60 times higher than that of a conventional Co/MgO catalyst [26]. Despite these advances, further research is needed as cobalt is more expensive than iron, and therefore, to justify its use in a large-scale ammonia synthesis process, cobalt catalyst activities should significantly exceed the industrial iron catalyst in terms of the ammonia synthesis rate, not only per catalyst weight, but also per catalyst volume that determines ammonia productivity in a reactor.

The aim of the work was to explore the prospects of Nd_2O_3 -supported Fe, Co, and Ni monometallic catalysts for ammonia synthesis. Nd_2O_3 was selected as the support in these investigations mainly due to its unique electronic and structural properties. In general, rare-earth oxides (REO) have been proven to be effective supports and promoters in ammonia synthesis [1]. Among various rare-earth elements, CeO_2 , La_2O_3 , Nd_2O_3 , and Pr_2O_3 oxides were found to be the most effective supports of Ru- and Co-based ammonia synthesis catalysts [28,29]. This is because rare-earth oxides exhibit moderate to strong basicity, which promotes the electron donation to the active metal sites (e.g., Ru, Fe, or Co). This electron donation facilitates $\text{N}\equiv\text{N}$ bond activation, a rate-determining step (RDS) of ammonia synthesis, by lowering the energy barrier for nitrogen dissociation. In addition, the rare-earth oxides possess a high thermal stability, making them suitable for use under the high-temperature conditions typical of ammonia synthesis. Combining with the interactions between the active metal and the rare-earth oxide, the improved stability and dispersion of the active metal during prolonged operation are observed [28,29]. Among CeO_2 , La_2O_3 , Nd_2O_3 , and Pr_2O_3 oxides, Nd_2O_3 has been less studied in the literature, highlighting the need for further developments. Moreover, neodymium oxide has recently attracted more attention due to the development of neodymium recycling technologies. NdFeB magnets are suggested as a potential Nd secondary resource due to their large availability and high economic value [30,31]. The studies show that Nd recycling is unlikely to be hindered by limits to recycled content in magnets, thus showing the approach for the upcycling of the recycled Nd [30,31]. The recycled Nd can be more economically feasible, making it possible to apply on a large scale. According to ref. [32], a techno-economic analysis of recycling of rare-earth elements from NdFeB magnet projected a net profit margin of 12–43 % and a global warming impact reduction by up to 73 % compared to the rare-earth oxides production routes in China. Some Chinese NdFeB magnet manufacturing companies have already established green manufacturing routes to recover REEs from spent magnets

[33]. The recycling of NdFeB magnet waste is also a concern for the EU and the US, which are working on technologies to recover REE to avoid the risks involved in the REE supply chain [33]. This is believed to open the possibility of using neodymium oxide in different catalytic reactions.

To explore the prospects of Nd_2O_3 -supported Fe, Co, and Ni monometallic catalysts for ammonia synthesis, a detailed series of X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), temperature-programmed reduction (TPR), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) experiments was performed. The catalytic performance in the ammonia synthesis reaction was evaluated at 400 and 470 °C and 6.3 MPa.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Support and catalyst synthesis

All chemicals used were from Merck and Acros Organics, or Chempur and of analytical grade.

The Nd_2O_3 support was prepared by the precipitation method. The proper amount of $\text{Nd}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in distilled water under stirring at 30 °C. Then, the solution of K_2CO_3 and KOH was added dropwise up to pH 11. The precipitate was aged at 65 °C for 24 h, then collected by filtration, washed and dried at 120 °C for 24 h. Finally, the sample was calcined at 500 °C for 5 h.

The Nd_2O_3 -supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts were prepared by wet impregnation. Nominal metal content was fixed at 10 wt%. The proper amount of the respective metal nitrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, or $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was dissolved in distilled water under stirring at room temperature (RT). Then, the Nd_2O_3 support was added to the metal nitrate solution, and the suspension was stirred at RT for 15 min and kept overnight. Then, the water was removed using a rotary evaporator, and the sample was dried at 120 °C for 24 h. Finally, the sample was calcined at 550 °C for 5 h. The obtained samples were denoted as Fe/ Nd_2O_3 , Co/ Nd_2O_3 and Ni/ Nd_2O_3 . The pre-catalysts were activated at 550 °C in hydrogen before the catalytic tests and characterisation. Unless otherwise stated (e.g., as-prepared catalyst, pre-catalyst), the catalysts mentioned in the manuscript refer to the reduced catalysts.

2.2. Characterisation

H_2 temperature-programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR) experiments were performed using a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 instrument. A 0.2 g pre-catalyst sample was heated to 900 °C at a rate of 10 °C min^{-1} under a flow of 10 % H_2/Ar mixture at 40 mL min^{-1} . The H_2 consumption was monitored by a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

N_2 physisorption measurements were performed using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 instrument at -196 °C. A support sample (0.5 g) was degassed under vacuum at 90 °C for 1 h and 300 °C for 4 h. A pre-catalyst sample (0.5 g) was firstly reduced at 550 °C for 12 h under a hydrogen flow (40 mL min^{-1}), followed by purging at 570 °C for 2 h under a helium flow (40 mL min^{-1}). The sample was subsequently degassed under vacuum at 200 °C for 2 h. The surface area was calculated using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method in the relative partial pressure range (P/P_0) from 0.05 to 0.3.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) at 40 kV and 40 mA. XRD pattern of the support was acquired without pre-treatment, while XRD patterns of the catalysts were acquired after reduction at 550 °C for 24 h under hydrogen flow. Data collection employed Bragg–Brentano (θ/θ) geometry over a 2θ range of 10–90° in continuous scan mode, with a step size of 0.03° and a counting time of 10 s per step. The data were analysed using the Rietveld refinement method with TOPAS 5 software.

Microscopic observations were conducted using a Talos F200X (FEI) microscope in STEM mode with a high-angle annular dark-field

(HAADF) detector and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy on a Bruker BD4 spectrometer. A pre-catalyst sample (0.5 g) was reduced at 550 °C for 24 h under a hydrogen flow (40 mL min⁻¹). The reduced catalyst was ground to a fine powder and dispersed in ethanol. A few drops of the dispersion were deposited onto a carbon-coated copper mesh TEM grid and left to dry overnight. STEM-derived metal dispersions were obtained according to ref. [34].

H₂ temperature-programmed desorption (H₂-TPD) experiments were performed using a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 instrument. A pre-catalyst sample (0.5 g) was reduced at 550 °C under H₂ (40 mL min⁻¹) for 18 h, followed by purging at 570 °C for 2 h under Ar (40 mL min⁻¹). The sample was cooled to 150 °C, then H₂ was introduced at 40 mL min⁻¹ for 15 min, and then further cooled to 0 °C for 15 min. After argon purging at 0 °C, H₂-TPD was conducted under argon (40 mL min⁻¹) with a 10 °C min⁻¹ ramp to 700 °C while continuously monitoring the H₂ desorption by TCD. The signal was normalised by sample mass.

CO₂ temperature-programmed desorption (CO₂-TPD) was conducted using a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 instrument. A pre-catalyst sample (0.2 g) was reduced at 550 °C under H₂ (40 mL min⁻¹) for 18 h, purged at 570 °C for 2 h under He (40 mL min⁻¹), and then cooled to 40 °C. CO₂ was introduced at 40 mL min⁻¹ for 2 h, followed by purging with helium at 40 °C until a stable baseline was achieved. CO₂-TPD was performed by heating the sample at 10 °C min⁻¹ to 600 °C under helium (40 mL min⁻¹). The CO₂ desorption was monitored by TCD. The signal was normalised by sample mass.

2.3. Catalytic activity tests

Ammonia synthesis activity was tested in a tubular flow reactor [35, 36]. A pre-catalyst sample (0.5 g) was activated under a H₂/N₂ (75/25 mol%) gas mixture at a total flow rate of 70 L h⁻¹ following a temperature program: 470 °C for 72 h, 520 °C for 24 h, 550 °C for 48 h. After activation, the reactor was pressurised to 6.3 MPa and heated to target temperatures (400 or 470 °C). Ammonia production was analysed interferometrically, and the synthesis rate was determined using a mass balance for a plug-flow differential reactor [35,36]. TOF values were calculated based on the STEM-derived dispersions, according to ref. [34]. The thermal stability of the catalysts was evaluated by conducting the tests at 470 °C and 6.3 MPa after overheating at 550 °C for about 150 h under atmospheric pressure.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Support characteristics

First, the characteristics of support were determined. The XRD pattern of Nd₂O₃ (Figure S1) revealed well-defined peaks attributable to the neodymium dioxide carbonate (Nd₂O₂CO₃) phases of monoclinic (PDF 23–0421) and hexagonal (PDF 37–0806) structures. These polymorphs are reported to be stable under ambient conditions [37]. As reported in the literature [37,38], to obtain pure neodymium oxide, calcination at > 700 °C is required [38]; however, this deteriorates the porous structure and significantly decreases the BET surface area (to about 2 m² g⁻¹ [38]). Such a low surface area often leads to decreased catalytic activity due to the reduced metal dispersion [38]. To avoid this adverse effect, a calcination temperature of 500 °C was selected. N₂ sorption studies of the obtained support showed that the support exhibited a type IV nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm (Figure S2) with H3 hysteresis loop, which is characteristic of mesoporous materials with slit pores. The BET surface area was calculated as 39.9 m² g⁻¹, and the pore volume was 0.33 g⁻¹. This high BET surface area allowed the catalyst to expose more active sites.

3.2. Catalyst characteristics

Second, the catalysts were evaluated using multiple techniques. The

metal content in the pre-catalysts was determined by XRF. The metal content was close to the nominal value, with a variation of ±1.0 wt% (Table 1). The metal deposition onto the supports caused a markable decrease in the surface area. This was due to the pores being blocked by metal nanoparticles [39]. The catalyst surface area was between 8.5 and 12.6 m² g_{cat}⁻¹, with the highest BET surface area for Ni/Nd₂O₃, followed by Co/Nd₂O₃ and Fe/Nd₂O₃. This result shows that Co/Nd₂O₃ and Ni/Nd₂O₃ were less prone to sintering than Fe/Nd₂O₃. This was further confirmed by measuring the surface area of spent catalysts. The most prominent decrease was observed for Fe/Nd₂O₃ (~24%), followed by Ni/Nd₂O₃ (~16%) and Co/Nd₂O₃ (~9%), indicating that the agglomeration of metal NPs was the main reason for the observed reduction of the BET surface area of spent catalysts.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to identify the crystal structure of the pre-catalysts and catalysts. Fig. 1a presents the XRD patterns of the pre-catalysts. The diffraction peaks assignable to the neodymium dioxide carbonate phases of monoclinic and hexagonal structures were visible, originating from the support (Figure S2). There were also the reflexes originating from the Fe, Co, and Ni species in the form of oxides: Fe as Fe₂O₃, Co as Co₃O₄, and Ni as NiO. There were significant changes in the phase composition after the reductive activation. The XRD patterns of the catalysts are shown in Fig. 1b.

The diffraction peaks corresponding to neodymium oxide (Nd₂O₃) phases of hexagonal (PDF 41–1089) and cubic (PDF 21–0579) structures were detected. This indicates that neodymium oxide was formed during the reductive activation. This agrees with the observations in ref. [40], where neodymium dioxide carbonate decomposes to neodymium oxide more easily under a reductive atmosphere than under air. There were also small diffraction peaks belonging to the metallic Fe cubic (bcc), Co hexagonal (hcp), and Ni cubic (fcc) phases in the respective XRD patterns. This indicates the complete reduction of the loaded metal species to their metallic state; however, the reliable determination of the metal crystal size was not feasible. No other peaks were observed in the XRD patterns, confirming the desired phase composition.

H₂-TPR was employed to study the reduction behaviour of the pre-catalysts, and the obtained profiles are shown in Fig. 2.

The H₂-TPR profiles exhibited several overlapping reduction peaks in the temperature range of 100–700 °C. The interpretation of the profiles is difficult since, besides the reduction of metal oxide species, the decomposition of neodymium dioxide carbonate (Nd₂O₂CO₃) occurred. Nd₂O₂CO₃ is reported to decompose to Nd₂O₃ and CO₂. CO₂ can react further with hydrogen, forming CH₄ [40]. These reactions occur at around 600 °C [40]. Fe/Nd₂O₃ pre-catalyst exhibited an overlapped peak at 473 °C. Fe was identified as Fe₂O₃; thus, it might be reduced in two stages: Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺ and Fe²⁺ to Fe⁰ [41]. The peak rise at 600 °C could be attributed to the decomposition of Nd₂O₂CO₃ as well as to the reduction of Fe oxide strongly interacting with the support. Co/Nd₂O₃ showed the presence of several overlapping peaks. Co was identified as Co₃O₄; thus, it might be reduced in two stages: Co³⁺ to Co²⁺ and Co²⁺ to Co⁰ [42]. The peak at 382 °C might be assigned to the Co³⁺ to Co²⁺ reduction, whereas the peak at 585 °C consists of two peaks, with the one plausibly corresponding to the reduction of Co²⁺ to Co⁰ and the second to the decomposition of Nd₂O₂CO₃. Ni/Nd₂O₃ showed the presence of the three reduction peaks at 243, 358, and 550 °C. Ni existed in the form of NiO; however, the presence of non-stoichiometric NiO (comprising Ni³⁺ ions) could not be excluded [43]. The peak at 243 °C might, therefore, be ascribed to the reduction of Ni³⁺ to Ni²⁺ [43]. The peak at 358 °C might be related to the reduction of NiO, which did not interact strongly with the support. The peak at 551 °C might be due to the reduction of NiO interacting strongly with the support; however, the decomposition of Nd₂O₂CO₃ contributed to this peak. It is generally seen for all three pre-catalysts that a temperature of 600 °C is required to reduce the metal oxide completely and to decompose the neodymium dioxide carbonate; however, it was confirmed that the catalysts were composed of metal and neodymium oxide phases already upon prolonged reduction at 550 °C (Fig. 1b).

Table 1
Physicochemical properties of the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts.

Catalyst	Metal content ^a (wt%)	BET surface area ^b (m ² g _{cat} ⁻¹)	Metal particle size ^c (nm)	Metal dispersion ^c (%)	H ₂ chemisorption ^d (μmol g _{cat} ⁻¹)
Fe/Nd ₂ O ₃	9.3	8.5 (6.5)	34	2.4	30
Co/Nd ₂ O ₃	9.2	11.3 (10.4)	14	6.1	40
Ni/Nd ₂ O ₃	9.0	12.6 (10.6)	8	8.3	34

^a Determined by XRF.

^b Determined by the BET method. The values in brackets are the BET surface area of the spent catalysts (after the ammonia synthesis reaction).

^c Determined by STEM.

^d Determined by H₂-TPD.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni (a) pre-catalysts and (b) catalysts.

Fig. 2. H₂-TPR profiles of the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni pre-catalysts.

HAADF-STEM images and EDX elemental mapping of the catalyst components are shown in Figs. 3–5.

The EDX elemental mapping showed that the Co and Ni particles were evenly distributed over the Nd₂O₃ support, whereas the distribution of Fe particles was ambiguous. The Co and Ni particles with rather uniform sizes and round shapes, with around 10 nm in diameter, were detected. The Fe particles were, in turn, of irregular shape and consisted of dense agglomerates of various sizes, probably due to partial oxidation in air. The results of particle size distribution showed that the average diameters of Fe, Co and Ni were 34, 14 and 8 nm, respectively. The STEM-derived metal dispersion followed the trend: Ni/Nd₂O₃ (8.3 %) > Co/Nd₂O₃ (6.1 %) > Fe/Nd₂O₃ (2.4 %). This clearly shows that Fe NPs were more prone to sintering and agglomeration than Co and Ni NPs. HR-TEM images (Fig. 6) confirmed the results of the XRD, which indicated the presence of Fe (bcc), Co (hcp), and Ni (fcc) structures (Fig. 1b).

CO₂-TPD was performed to study the carbon dioxide adsorption properties, aiming to evaluate the surface basicity. Since the adsorption of CO₂ on the metal phase is rather weak, the desorption peaks were associated with the presence of basic sites on neodymium oxide. The obtained CO₂-TPD profiles (Fig. 7a) can be divided into two temperature ranges (50–150 and 200–450 °C), corresponding to the weak and medium-strength basic sites. It was reported that the weak basic sites are recognised as the Brønsted basic sites and are associated with the surface hydroxyl groups [44,45]. The medium and strong basic sites are recognised as Lewis basic sites and are assignable to the metal-oxygen pairs,

Fig. 3. HAADF-STEM images and EDX maps of the Fe/Nd₂O₃ catalyst. (a) Overlay EDX mapping of Fe and Nd. (b) HAADF-STEM image. EDX mapping of (c) Fe, (d) Nd, and (e) O.

Fig. 4. HAADF-STEM images and EDX maps of the Co/Nd₂O₃ catalyst. (a) Overlay EDX mapping of Co and Nd. (b) HAADF-STEM image. EDX mapping of (c) Co, (d) Nd, and (e) O.

and the low-coordination oxygen anions (O²⁻) [45]. The catalysts showed very similar CO₂ desorption profiles to that of the support (Figure S3), each consisting of a minor peak at 100 °C and a major peak at 300 °C, indicating the abundance of medium basic sites. CO₂ desorption observed at 300 °C was the greatest on Ni/Nd₂O₃, intermediate on Co/Nd₂O₃, and least on Fe/Nd₂O₃. It was reported that medium- and strong-strength basic sites are of significant importance for ammonia synthesis as they promote the electron transfer to active sites, thus facilitating nitrogen dissociative adsorption, recognised as the rate-determining step (RDS) of the ammonia synthesis reaction [1].

The total amount of CO₂ desorbed was used as a metric of basicity. The highest basic site number observed for Nd₂O₃ was expected (237 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹) since the metal deposition onto the support can block the acid-base sites [46]. Ni/Nd₂O₃ (95 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹) exhibited the highest basic site number among the catalysts, followed by Co/Nd₂O₃ (75 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹) and Fe/Nd₂O₃ (53 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹) (Fig. 7b). These results reveal that the surface basicity of Ni/Nd₂O₃ was stronger than that of Co/Nd₂O₃ and Fe/Nd₂O₃. Also, Ni/Nd₂O₃ had the highest basic site density (7.6 μmol m⁻²), followed by Co/Nd₂O₃ (6.7 μmol m⁻²) and Fe/Nd₂O₃ (6.3 μmol m⁻²); however, the differences were not as significant as that of the basic site

number (Fig. 7b).

H₂-TPD was performed to study the hydrogen adsorption properties on the metal surfaces, aiming to evaluate the nature of the active sites. The obtained H₂-TPD profiles (Fig. 8) can be divided into three temperature ranges at 50–250 °C, 250–650 °C, and > 650 °C. The peak at 150 and 400 °C was associated with the desorption of H₂ weakly and intermediately bound to the metal surface, whereas the presence of the H₂ desorption peak above 600 °C was ascribed to the strong chemisorption state of H₂ on the metal surfaces [47,48]. Fe/Nd₂O₃ showed the presence of one distinct desorption peak at around 400 °C and one above 700 °C. Co/Nd₂O₃ possessed two distinct H₂ desorption peaks at 98 and 547 °C, whereas Ni/Nd₂O₃ showed one distinct peak at 96 °C and one broad peak from 200 to 700 °C. These results indicate that the hydrogen adsorption properties strongly depend on the metal. Co/Nd₂O₃ possessed more diverse adsorption sites for hydrogen compared to Fe/Nd₂O₃ and Ni/Nd₂O₃, which is known to be beneficial for efficient hydrogen activation [40].

H₂-TPD was also used to roughly estimate the metal dispersion based on the amount of H₂ desorption (Table 1). Assuming the same adsorbate stoichiometry for all catalysts (stoichiometric ratio of H₂ to iron, cobalt,

Fig. 5. HAADF-STEM images and EDX maps of the Ni/Nd₂O₃ catalyst. (a) Overlay EDX mapping of Ni and Nd. (b) HAADF-STEM image. EDX mapping of (c) Ni, (d) Nd, and (e) O.

Fig. 6. HR-TEM images of (a) Fe/Nd₂O₃, (b) Co/Nd₂O₃, and (c) Ni/Nd₂O₃ catalysts.

Fig. 7. (a) CO₂-TPD profiles and (b) number and density of basic sites of the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts.

and nickel of 2), the obtained dispersions followed the trend Co/Nd₂O₃ (5.1 %) > Ni/Nd₂O₃ (4.4 %) > Fe/Nd₂O₃ (3.6 %). This is not consistent with the trend obtained from the STEM particle size distribution: Ni/Nd₂O₃ (8.3 %) > Co/Nd₂O₃ (6.1 %) > Fe/Nd₂O₃ (2.4 %). The reasons might be the set of adsorption conditions, uncertainties in adsorbate

stoichiometry, and/or incomplete desorption of hydrogen during the desorption stage [34]. Thus, the H₂-TPD results provide only a general comparison of the hydrogen adsorption behaviour on the metal surfaces (not quantitative). The following discussion on the catalytic properties of different types of metal species was therefore based on the

Fig. 8. H₂-TPD profiles of the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Ce, and Ni catalysts.

STEM-derived dispersions.

The ammonia synthesis performance was evaluated at 470 °C and 6.3 MPa. Fig. 9a compares the catalytic performance (NH₃ formation rate and TOF) of Fe/Nd₂O₃, Co/Nd₂O₃, and Ni/Nd₂O₃.

There were significant differences in the activities between the catalysts. The NH₃ synthesis rate of Co/Nd₂O₃ (52 mmol_{NH₃} g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹) was around 2 times higher than that of Fe/Nd₂O₃ (28 mmol_{NH₃} g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹) and around 17 times higher than that of Ni/Nd₂O₃ (3 mmol_{NH₃} g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹). This trend in the reaction rates agrees with the literature [46]. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 9b, all three catalysts showed no obvious sign of deactivation after overheating at 550 °C for about 150 h; a slight decrease in ammonia synthesis rate of around 3 % was observed for Co/Nd₂O₃, whereas a slight increase in ammonia synthesis rate of around 2–3 % was observed for Fe/Nd₂O₃ and Ni/Nd₂O₃, respectively. To evaluate the intrinsic reaction rates (reflected as the TOF), the differences in metal dispersion evaluated by STEM had to be taken into account. The calculated TOFs followed a different trend from that of the ammonia formation rates; the highest TOF was observed for Fe/Nd₂O₃ (0.2 s⁻¹), followed by Co/Nd₂O₃ (0.15 s⁻¹) and Ni/Nd₂O₃ (0.01 s⁻¹) (Fig. 9a). Importantly, the TOF values are in accordance with the

reported volcano-shaped relation between the ammonia synthesis activity of the pure metals [9,10]. It was reported that the intrinsic rates are dependent on the metal, and the order of activity follows the trend: Ru > Os > Fe > Co > Mo > Ni. The superior ammonia synthesis rate of the Co/Nd₂O₃ over Fe/Nd₂O₃ could be explained by the better Co metal dispersion than Fe metal (Table 1). Thus, despite the higher intrinsic activity of Fe active sites, a higher number of Co active sites led to the enhancement of the ammonia formation rate. These results prove that despite the lower intrinsic activities of pure Co than Fe, its activity can be enhanced by proper support choice. The Co NPs, compared to the Fe NPs, were better distributed on the Nd₂O₃ support (Table 1), which, in combination with strong basicity and diverse hydrogen adsorption sites (Figs. 7 and 8), resulted in improved ammonia synthesis rates. Indeed, in the literature, one can find the cobalt catalysts of much higher activity compared to the iron catalysts, even though pure Co is not as active as pure Fe in the ammonia synthesis reaction [1,18,48]. Ni/Nd₂O₃ exhibited almost no activity in the ammonia synthesis reaction, although favourable physicochemical properties (Table 1 and Fig. 7). This is consistent with previous reports in which Ni supported on common oxide supports such as Al₂O₃, MgO, CeO₂, and La₂O₃ exhibits almost no activity in ammonia synthesis [1]. However, recent reports indicate that there is a possibility of obtaining an efficient nickel catalyst for ammonia synthesis when advanced catalyst design is used [49,50]. For example, Ye et al. [49] studied the binary intermetallic LaNi₅ catalysts and compared their activity to Ni supported on various supports (La₂O₃, MgO, active carbon (AC), or even C12A7:e⁻). The supported Ni catalysts showed much lower activity for ammonia synthesis compared to LaNi₅, mainly due to the differences in electronic structure and N₂ activation ability. Even Ni-loaded on C12A7:e⁻, which has a low work function and can donate electrons, the activity was not significantly improved. This suggests that electron donation from the common oxide supports (e.g., Al₂O₃, MgO, CeO₂, and La₂O₃) to Ni is not sufficient to alter its electronic structure required for efficient N₂ activation. For the binary intermetallic LaNi₅ catalysts, Ye et al. revealed that LaNi₅ undergoes surface decomposition during ammonia synthesis, forming a self-organised Ni–LaN core–shell structure. This nanostructure exhibited high catalytic activity, about 20 times higher than bulk LaNi₅ and significantly higher (about 2 orders of magnitude) than the supported Ni catalysts. It was revealed that the formation of the Ni–LaN core–shell structures resulted in a negatively charged Ni, due to the large work function gap between Ni (5.2 eV) and LaN (2.8 eV), enabling effective charge transfer to Ni, facilitating N₂ activation and boosting catalytic activity. In another study, Gao et al. [50] reported that Ni can be highly active in ammonia synthesis when promoted with barium hydride

Fig. 9. Catalytic performance of Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts for ammonia synthesis. (a) NH₃ synthesis rate and turnover frequency (TOF) at 470 °C and 6.3 MPa. (b) Time-on-stream performance at 470 °C and 6.3 MPa. The catalysts were overheated at 550 °C during the intervals between measurements.

(BaH₂). BaH₂ is a strong hydride donor. The results showed that it transfers hydride to Ni, leading to the formation of highly reactive ternary [Ba–H–Ni] species. These [Ba–H–Ni] interfacial sites significantly improve N₂ activation. The formed [Ba–Ni–N–H] intermediates can be further hydrogenated to NH₃. This synergistic effect between Ni and BaH₂ significantly decreased the apparent activation energy of ammonia synthesis, from 150 kJ mol⁻¹ (for bare Ni–Mg–O) to 87 kJ mol⁻¹ after the addition of BaH₂. This suggests a change in the reaction mechanism, likely due to the participation of BaH₂ in both nitrogen fixation and hydrogenation steps. The presented results confirm our observation. The conventional supported Ni catalysts show almost no activity in ammonia synthesis. This is due to the fact that electron donation from these supports to Ni is not sufficient to alter its electronic structure required for efficient N₂ activation. This is only possible when strong electron donors are used, as revealed by Ye and Gao et al. [49,50]. These all highlight the crucial role of the promotion in catalyst development. The properly selected support and promoters provide structural stability and, in combination with electronic promotion, make the catalysts efficient and stable in ammonia synthesis [9].

3.3. Practical considerations

For industrial applications, the key challenge is to design a cost-effective, highly active and stable catalyst tailored to the harsh ammonia synthesis conditions. While Ru- and Co-based catalysts have received interest as a new generation of ammonia synthesis catalysts [51], there are no studies on Ni and Fe-based catalysts supported on rare-earth oxides. Therefore, Table 2 shows only the comparison of the catalytic activity of Co-based catalysts for ammonia synthesis in terms of reaction rate and intrinsic reaction rate (reflected as the TOF value). Co/Nd₂O₃ outperformed the literature-reported catalysts under the same reaction conditions. Moreover, the Fe/Nd₂O₃ catalyst outperformed most of the literature-reported catalysts, indicating the prospects of Co/Nd₂O₃ and Fe/Nd₂O₃ for further development.

The catalytic performance of Fe/Nd₂O₃, Co/Nd₂O₃, and Ni/Nd₂O₃ for ammonia synthesis was further revealed by comparison to the industrial fused Fe catalysts and Ru catalyst (Table 3). The catalyst activity was compared at 400 °C and under a relatively high pressure of 6.3–10 MPa. The benchmark catalysts and reaction conditions were selected to evaluate the feasibility for industrial implementation. Indeed, the synthesis loop in the KAAP process operates at a pressure of around 9 MPa while using a ruthenium catalyst supported on active carbon (Ru/AC) [1]. Ammonia synthesis plants that have applied the KAAP process can produce more than 2000 tonnes per day. However, the number of plants is only seven in the world, and the conventional iron-based catalysts operating at > 15 MPa and > 400 °C are still general [1,54,55]. Although a direct comparison was not possible due to the different reaction pressures, it can be seen that the fused iron catalysts exhibited higher reaction rates per mass of catalyst; however, the

Table 2

Comparison of ammonia synthesis performance over the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts with the literature-reported Co catalysts. Fe, Co or Ni metal loading was about 10 wt%. Reaction conditions: 470 °C, 6.3 MPa, H₂/N₂ = 3.

Catalyst	NH ₃ synthesis rate (mmol _{NH₃} g _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	TOF (s ⁻¹)	Ref.
Fe/Nd ₂ O ₃	28	0.20	This work
Co/Nd ₂ O ₃	52	0.15	
Ni/Nd ₂ O ₃	3	0.01	
Co/La ₂ O ₃	47	0.15	
CoNd ₂ O ₃	18	0.06	
Co/Sm ₂ O ₃	8	0.02	[52]
Co/Eu ₂ O ₃	11	0.03	
Co/Gd ₂ O ₃	11	0.02	
Co/MgO	12	N/A	[53]
Co/La ₂ O ₃	31	N/A	

N/A = not available.

Table 3

Comparison of ammonia synthesis performance over the Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni catalysts with the industrial fused Fe catalysts.

Catalyst	Pressure (MPa)	Temperature (°C)	NH ₃ synthesis rate		Ref.
			(mmol _{NH₃} g _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	(mmol _{NH₃} g _{metal} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	
Fe/Nd ₂ O ₃	6.3	400	9	97	This work
Co/Nd ₂ O ₃			19	207	
Ni/Nd ₂ O ₃			1	11	
PS-3-INSa	9	400	150	160	[56]
KM1b	9	400	181	193	[56]
KM1Rc	10	400	163	173	[15]
Ba–K–Ru/C	10	400	358	3580	[57]

^a PS-3-INS is an unreduced multi-promoted fused Fe catalyst provided by Grupa Azoty S.A. (Tarnów).

^b KM1 is an unreduced multi-promoted fused Fe catalyst provided by Haldor Topsøe.

^c KM1R is a pre-reduced multi-promoted fused Fe catalyst provided by Haldor Topsøe.

reaction rate per mass of metal was higher for the Co/Nd₂O₃ catalyst. This indicates that the Co/Nd₂O₃ catalyst possessed active sites of higher intrinsic activity than the commercial iron catalysts, but further research is needed to improve the overall catalyst activity, and strategies such as the addition of promoters are known to be effective [1]. Compared to the Ru-based catalyst, a much lower reaction rate per mass of catalyst and per mass of metal was observed for the Co-based catalysts; however, it should be noted that Ru-based catalysts are recognised as the most active ammonia synthesis catalysts reported to date [1]. Nevertheless, it is believed that Nd₂O₃-supported Fe and Co catalysts are promising ammonia synthesis catalysts, especially taking into account that the listed Fe- and Ru-based catalysts (Table 3) are of optimised composition, whereas our catalysts have not been optimised yet.

Although the catalyst cost is often a topic of discussion, in practice, it is a small percentage of the overall cost of ammonia production. A calculation described in ref. [58] pointed out that for the industrial fused Fe catalysts, the catalyst cost comprises less than 0.6 % of the total cost of ammonia production. For the Ru/C catalyst, the calculations described in ref. [59] showed that the catalyst cost comprises less than 9 % of the total cost of ammonia production. This suggests that if a catalyst is sufficiently active and stable, its use in industrial ammonia synthesis can be justified. Although the Ru-based catalysts are of very high activity, the global ruthenium production rate is reported at around only 35.5 tonnes per year. Therefore, globally, most ammonia synthesis plants rely on fused iron catalysts operating under very harsh reaction conditions (>15 MPa and >400 °C [1]). Currently, a Ru/CeO₂ catalyst is considered as a candidate for use in small ammonia plants powered by renewable energy that can be implemented in areas with local ammonia demand [22]. This is especially interesting as cerium oxide is more expensive than other oxidic supports such as magnesium oxide [22]. A growing demand for rare-earth elements (REEs) raises concerns about the cost-effectiveness of using REEs in industrial ammonia synthesis. The REE market is projected towards growth from 5.3 billion USD (2021) to 9.6 billion USD by 2026 at an annual growth rate of 12.3 %. It is also projected that there will be significant demand growth for neodymium oxide, which is a key component in the production of NdFeB magnets. By 2020, the price of neodymium oxide was US\$50 kg⁻¹, whereas in 2025, it is expected to reach US\$78 kg⁻¹ [60]. However, it can be supposed that using neodymium oxide as the support for Co and Fe ammonia synthesis will not be a problem in terms of costs, especially taking into account the huge difference in price between the industrially implemented Ru catalyst and the Co catalyst. The ruthenium price is US\$9523 kg⁻¹ [61], whereas the cobalt price varies between US\$30 kg⁻¹ and US\$90 kg⁻¹ [62]. As such, the key aspect is to develop a highly active and stable catalyst.

Neodymium oxide has recently attracted more attention due to the

development of neodymium recycling technologies. NdFeB magnets are suggested as a potential Nd secondary resource due to their large availability and high economic value [30–32]. EU regulations imply that at least 15 % of the EU annual consumption of REE permanent magnets should be covered by recycling capacities by 2030 [63]. Currently, researchers in the EU Horizon Europe project NEO-CYCLE consortium are working to develop an efficient recycling method to recover the critical raw materials from spent NdFeB magnets sourced from hard disk drives (HDDs) [64]. The project aims to demonstrate at TRL6 the sustainable upcycling of spent NdFeB magnets, reaching high-quality end products for industries, including pharmaceuticals, ammonia production, fertilisers, and polymers [64]. The project leads the charge in demonstrating novel processes such as hydrometallurgical and electrochemical approaches [64]. Such initiatives will further incentivise efforts to develop efficient recycling strategies to make the application of REE more feasible. Moreover, it should be noted that the spent catalyst can also be recycled to recover the critical raw materials. For the spent iron ammonia synthesis catalysts, the recycling is based on reoxidation of the metallic iron to iron oxide, followed by remelting and annealing [58]. For the ruthenium catalysts, some patents describe the methods based on hydrometallurgy for the recovery of ruthenium from the used Ru/MgO and Ru/Al₂O₃ catalysts [65,66]. The Ru recovery of more than 94 % can be achieved [65,66]. The Co catalysts can also be recycled using the above methods. According to the literature [67], the Co recovery from spent Co–Mn catalysts of more than 95 % can be achieved.

To sum up this section, we analysed and reviewed the prospects of using Nd₂O₃-supported Co and Fe catalysts for ammonia synthesis in terms of activity, stability, cost of production and recycling technologies. Based on these considerations, it can be concluded that further improvement in catalyst activity is essential. The current study provides a premise for further development, especially taking into account the possibility of using recycled neodymium oxide, thus contributing to lowering the overall catalyst production cost.

4. Conclusions

In this study, Nd₂O₃-supported Fe, Co, and Ni monometallic catalysts were synthesised using the wet impregnation method and studied in the ammonia synthesis reaction. The effect of active metal on the physico-chemical and catalytic properties was explored. The Co/Nd₂O₃ catalyst showed a higher ammonia synthesis rate compared to the Fe/Nd₂O₃ and Ni/Nd₂O₃ catalysts. However, when comparing the intrinsic reaction rates, Fe/Nd₂O₃ showed a higher TOF than Co/Nd₂O₃ and Ni/Nd₂O₃. The obtained trend in the TOFs (Fe > Co > Ni) is in accordance with the reported volcano-shaped trend of ammonia synthesis activity of pure metals. The characterisation studies revealed that the high ammonia synthesis rate over Co/Nd₂O₃ was due to the good Co metal dispersion over the support, as well as the more diverse hydrogen adsorption sites. The Co NPs were stable and less prone to sintering under reaction conditions than Fe NPs. Therefore, despite the lower intrinsic active site activity of Co/Nd₂O₃ relative to Fe/Nd₂O₃, the abundance of the cobalt active sites resulted in a high ammonia formation rate. The Ni/Nd₂O₃ catalyst exhibited the lowest activity, showing almost no activity in ammonia synthesis. This work also shows the potential of cobalt-based catalysts for efficient ammonia synthesis.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wioletta Raróg-Pilecka: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Hubert Ronduda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Andrzej Ostrowski:** Methodology, Investigation. **Kamil Sobczak:** Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Małgorzata Lemańska:** Methodology, Investigation. **Wojciech Patkowski:** Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115535](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115535)

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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